

Supporting Information

Selective coupling of bio-derived aliphatic alcohols with acetone using hydrotalcite derived Mg-Al porous metal oxide and Raney Nickel

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1. Materials and methods

1.1. Reagents and solvents

The chemicals were used as received, unless otherwise specified.

Reagents: Acetone (99.9%) was purchased from Merck. Ethanol (dehydrated) was purchased from Biosolve BV, The Netherlands. 1-butanol (99%) and 6-undecanone (98%) were purchased from TCI EUROPE N.V. 2-Heptanone (99%), 2-heptanol (99%) and dodecane ($\geq 99.0\%$) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich. 2-Ethylhexanol (99%) was purchased from Alfa Aesar.

Catalysts and catalyst precursors: $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\geq 98\%$), $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\geq 99.0\%$), $\text{Ni}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($> 99.0\%$), $\text{Co}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99.0%) and $\text{Zn}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (99.0%) were purchased from Alfa Aesar. Dodecane ($\geq 99.0\%$), Raney[®] Nickel 2800 (batch number: STBG7490), $\text{Ni}@\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{-SiO}_2$ (batch number: #MKBS9159V) catalyst were purchased from Sigma Aldrich.

Solvents: Methanol anhydrous (99%) and hexane (99%) was purchased from Acros. Heptane HPLC grade (99.5%) was purchased from Boom BV.

1.2. Equipment and Analysis

Gas chromatography with a flame ionization detector (GC-FID) was performed using a Hewlett Packard 6890 series equipped with a HP-5 capillary column using nitrogen as carrier gas. Gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS) was performed using a Shimadzu GC-2010 plus system equipped with a GCMS QP2010 GC SE detector and a HP5 column (30 m x 0.25 mm x 0.25 μm) using Helium as a carrier gas. Gas chromatography with a thermal conductivity detector (GC-TCD) was performed using a Hewlett Packard 5890 series II equipped with a Agilent Technologies HP-Molesieve 30 m x 0.53 mm x 50 μm . The columns were flushed for 30 seconds with gas sample before starting the measurement. A reference gas with known composition was (55.19% H_2 , 19.70% CH_4 , 3.00% CO , 18.10% CO_2 , 0.51% ethylene, 1.49% ethane, 0.51% propylene and 1.5% propane) used for peak identification and quantification.

Powder X-ray analysis was performed on a Bruker XRD diffractometer using $\text{Cu K}\alpha$ radiation and the spectra were recorded in the 2θ angle range of 10° - 70° . Elemental analysis was performed on a Perkin Elmer instrument (Optima 7000DV). TEM measurements were performed on a FEI Tecnai T20 electron microscope operating at 200 keV. For TEM and EDX measurements the catalysts were suspended in abs. EtOH under ultrasonication and placed on a copper grid. Elemental distribution was measured in STEM mode using a HAADF detector and an X-max 80 EDX detector (Oxford instruments).

1.3. Synthesis of PMO

The HT (hydrotalcite) catalyst precursor was prepared by a coprecipitation method, according to literature procedures.^{1,2,3} A solution containing $\text{MgCl}_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.15 mol, 30.05 g), $\text{AlCl}_3 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.05 mol, 12.07 g) in deionized water (0.2 L) was slowly added to an aqueous solution (0.2 L) of Na_2CO_3 (0.05 mol, 5.3 g) at 60°C under vigorous stirring. The pH was carefully maintained between 9 and 10 by adjusting with frequent additions of an aqueous solution of NaOH (1 M). The mixture was vigorously stirred for 72 h at 60°C . After cooling to

room temperature, the suspension was filtered, and the solid was washed with deionized water and resuspended into a solution of Na_2CO_3 (2M) which was stirred for 24 hours at 40°C. After the catalyst precursor was filtered and washed with deionized water until the washings were chloride-free (tested with AgNO_3 solution). The solid was dried at 120 °C overnight, and the hydrotalcite precursor (HTC) was obtained as a white powder (15.1 g). The corresponding porous metal oxide (PMO) was obtained after calcining a portion of the HTC material at 460 °C for 24 h. Elemental analyses were performed on a Perkin Elmer instrument (Optima 7000DV) after full solubilisation of the PMO catalyst in diluted nitric acid or *aqua regia* in case of transition metal doped PMOs. The results of the ICP measurements can be found in the catalyst characterisation paragraph (See paragraph 4).

The other doped hydrotalcites (Cu20PMO, Cu10Ni10PMO, Cu10Zn10PMO, Ni20PMO, Co20PMO) were prepared by replacing a portion of the Mg^{2+} ions with additional metal dopants, otherwise following the procedure above. In Cu20PMO, Ni20PMO and Co20PMO, 20 mol % of the Mg^{2+} were replaced by the corresponding two valent metal ions Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} respectively. In the Cu10Ni10PMO and Cu10Zn10PMO, 10 mol % of Mg^{2+} was replaced by Cu ions while 10 mol % was replaced by Ni and Zn respectively. The Ni20PMO catalyst was reduced in a tube furnace oven an atmosphere of pure hydrogen flow for four hours at 500°C and cooled down to room temperature and stored under Ar.

1.4. Representative procedures for catalytic runs

1.4.1. Catalytic coupling of acetone with 1-butanol or ABE mixture

The 15 mg Raney® Nickel slurry was placed in a Swagelok stainless steel microreactor (10 mL) equipped with a teflon coated magnetic stirring bar followed by the rapid addition of 1-butanol (5.46 mmol, 0.5 mL), acetone (2.7 mmol, 0.2 mL), and dodecane (0.22mmol, 50 μL , internal standard). Next, 200mg Mg-Al-PMO and heptane (2,1mL) solvent were added. The reactor was sealed and placed in an aluminium block pre-heated at the desired temperature. After the indicated reaction time, the microreactor was cooled down with an ice-water bath and subsequently carefully opened. The liquid sample as well as the catalyst were quantitatively transferred to a 15 mL centrifuge tube. Additional MeOH (2*1 mL) was used to wash the reactor and recover all catalyst residues. After centrifugation, the solution was transferred into a glass vial, washed four times with 2mL MeOH and analyzed by GC-FID as described in section 1.5.1 below in order to determine the 1-butanol and acetone conversion and selectivity of the products. If the mixture was to be hydrodeoxygenated, the reactions were performed in hexane instead of heptane in order to avoid overlap of the solvent with valuable products in the C7 region.

For coupling of ABE mixture acetone (2.9mmol, 0.21mL), butanol (4.6mmol, 0.42mL) and ethanol (1.2mmol, 70 μL) were used as substrate otherwise the procedure was identical. The ratio of A:B:E is kept at 2.3:3.7:1 molar ratio as expected from the mixture accessible directly from ABE fermentation.

1.4.2. Hydrodeoxygenation of ketones to alkanes

The mixture of chain elongated ketones obtained following the previous procedure, (or model compound: 2-heptanone) in hexane (~10mL) were loaded into a 15mL autoclave equipped with a magnetic stirring bar and 100 mg Ni@Al₂O₃-SiO₂ catalyst. The reactor was additionally purged with H₂ three times then pressurized to 40 bar, the autoclave was placed in a metal block preheated at 220 °C and the reaction proceeded for 12h. After, the reactor was cooled down by compressed air and ice water bath respectively. The content of the reactor was transferred to a 15mL centrifuge tube and the reactor was washed with additional amounts (5* 0.5 mL) of cold hexane. The catalyst was separated by centrifugation, a sample from the liquid phase was injected to GC-MS and parallel to GC-FID and the carbon yield was determined as specified in 1.5.2.

1.5. Product Analysis

1.5.1. Analysis of the mixture obtained upon coupling of acetone and 1-butanol or ABE

After separation of reaction mixture from the solids as described in 1.4.1. above, the solution was analyzed by GC-FID and GC-MS. The GC-MS trace was used for identification of all major compounds. In addition, on GC-FID, the identity of the compounds was verified by injection of pure reference standards.

Conversion of substrates were determined based on calibration curves and dodecane as internal standard on GC-FID. Selectivity values were given by GC-FID area percentages. Quantification of weight of alkanes was done in the stage after hydrodeoxygenation.

1.5.2. Analysis of the products obtained upon hydrodeoxygenation

After obtaining samples from the catalytic reactions as described in 1.4.2. above, the solution was analyzed by GC-FID and the identity of the compounds was verified by GC-MS and authentic standards when necessary.

Quantification of conversion of starting material was carried out by GC-FID with the use of calibration curves and dodecane as internal standard. Conversion and yield values were calculated based on the equations shown below.

Quantification of alkene mixture derived from AB and ABE coupling:

In order to calculate the yield of alkanes obtained after hydrodeoxygenation reaction, internal standard dodecane (C₁₂H₂₆) was added before reaction. Sensitivity factors of the products were obtained by ECN-based calculations due to the complexity of product mixture.⁴

The weight of alkanes of different chain length (W_x) was calculated based on the equation:

$$W_x = \frac{C_{12} \cdot A_x \cdot W_{12} \cdot M_x}{C_x \cdot A_{12} \cdot M_{12}} \quad \text{Equation S1}$$

Mx: molar mass of the alkanes with certain chain length; **Cx**: carbon number of the alkanes with certain chain length; **Ax**: summary of peak areas of products have the same chain length. **C12**: carbon number of internal standard; **A12**: area of internal standard; **W12**: weight of internal standard; **M12**: molar mass of internal standard.

For the carbon content in alkanes we use the chemical formula C_nH_{2n+2} as they are linear or branched alkanes.

So the carbon content in the alkane mixture obtained upon coupling of AB mixture and subsequent HDO is 50.4 mg (60.0×84%) for C7 and 207.1 mg (244.7×84.62%) for C11.

1.5.3. Analysis of the gas phase of a catalytic coupling reaction

The gas phase of a reaction with Raney® Nickel with PMO was analyzed by GC-TCD after reaction using a 15 mL autoclave (reaction conditions: 2.1 mL Heptane, 0.2 mL acetone, 0.5 mL 1-butanol, 15mg Raney® Nickel, 0.2g PMO catalyst, 200 °C, 12h, 1bar of Argon). During the reaction, the pressure increased to 10 bar at 200 °C and decreased to ~1 bar when cooling to room temperature. Main compounds in the gas phase included: methane, propane, H₂, CO, and CO₂.

2. Experimental data related to the catalytic coupling of AB or ABE mixtures

Table S1. Screening of various PMO catalysts containing different metal dopants in the catalytic coupling of acetone with 1-butanol.

Catalyst	Conversion (%)		Selectivity (%)								
	1-BuOH	Acetone	MIBUK	4-methyl-pentan-2-ol	2-heptanone	2-heptanol	Butyl-Butyrate	2-ethylhexanol	6-undecanone	6-undecanol	Higher MW. Products
Cu20PMO	49.9	55.4	1.5	1.5	23	34	30	2	3	0	0
Cu10Zn10PMO	41.3	49.4	3	1.5	34	27	24	2	5	0	0
Cu10Ni10PMO	46.1	64.5	2	0.3	56	13	7	6	13	0	0
Ni20PMO	29.0	58.3	0.4	0	40	5	0	2	10	3	27
Co20PMO	28.5	48.9	0	0	47	5	0.5	1	10	6	11

Table S2. Evaluating various Ni containing catalyst in the catalytic coupling of acetone with 1-butanol.

Catalysts		Conversion (%)		Selectivity (%)							
Base (200mg)	Raney® Ni (mg)	1-BuOH	Acetone	MIBUK	4-methyl-pentan-2-ol	2-heptanone	2-heptanol	2-ethylhexanol	6-undecanone	6-undecanol	Higher MW. products
PMO	-	18.9	66.8	1	2	8	3	0.7	0	0	78.6
-	15	21.5	15.8	4	17	61	0	0	0	0	0
H ₂ activated Ni20PMO (500°C)	0	63.7	78.7	0	0	22	28	4	20	5	10
H ₂ activated Ni20PMO (600°C)	0	74	84.1	0	0	28	26	3.8	22.4	4.7	7.3

Table S3. Evaluating the effect of increasing substrate loading in the catalytic coupling of acetone with 1-butanol.

Substrate (mmol)		(mL)	Conversion (%)		Selectivity (%)						
Acetone	1-BuOH	Heptane	1-BuOH	Acetone	MIBUK	2-heptanone	2-heptanol	2-ethylhexanol	6-undecanone	6-undecanol	Higher MW.
10.9	21.9	0	47.5	75.5	2	57	11	2.5	19	0	1.1
5.5	10.9	1.4	69.1	89.5	0.8	31	20	3.7	34	2	2.3
2.7	5.5	2.1	98.6	88.9	0	17	6	0	59	12	5.9
1.4	2.7	2.45	96.9	87.6	0	21	3	0	57	6	7.9

Figure S1. Variation of acetone to 1-butanol ratio between 1.9, 2.0, 2.1 in the catalytic coupling of acetone with 1-butanol.

Table S4. Variation of acetone to 1-butanol ratio between 1.9, 2.0, 2.1 in the catalytic coupling of acetone with 1-butanol.

Substrate amount (mmol)			Molar ratio	Conversion (%)		Selectivity (%)						
Total	Acetone	1-BuOH		1-BuOH	Acetone	MIBUK	2-heptanone	2-heptanol	2-ethylhexanol	6-undecanone	6-undecanol	Higher MW. Products
7.9	2.7	5.2	1:1.9	98.1	94.2	<0.1	20	6	2	52	10	5.6
8.2	2.7	5.5	1:2	98.5	88.5	<0.1	17	6	0	59	12	7.0
8.5	2.7	5.7	1:2.1	98.5	93	<0.1	17	6	0	53	11	5.0

Figure S2. Variation of reaction temperature between 180-220°C in the catalytic coupling of acetone with 1-butanol.

Table S5. Variation of reaction temperature between 180-220°C in the catalytic coupling of acetone with 1-butanol.

Temperature (°C)	Conversion (%)		Selectivity (%)						
	1-BuOH	Acetone	MIBUK	2-heptanone	2-heptanol	2-ethylhexanol	6-undecanone	6-undecanol	Higher MW. Products
180	90.3	94.2	<0.1	9	9	2	50	16	8.2
200	99.9	88.6	0.1	17	6	0	59	12	7.0
220	99.9	88.3	<0.1	24	5	0	50	7	6.5

Figure S3. Testing the reproducibility of results in the catalytic coupling of acetone with 1-butanol.

Table S6. Testing the reproducibility of results in the catalytic coupling of acetone with 1-butanol.

#	Conversion (%)		Selectivity (%)						
	1-BuOH	Acetone	MIBUK	2-heptanone	2-heptanol	2-ethylhexanol	6-undecanone	6-undecanol	Higher MW. products
1	99.9	88.7	0.1	14.5	3	0.3	60.5	7.5	5.0
2	99.9	89.6	0.1	11	3	0.1	62	9.0	9.8
3	99.9	88.4	0.1	12	2.5	0.1	62	8.0	6.3

Table S7. Variation of reaction time between 1.25-10 h in the catalytic coupling of acetone with 1-butanol.

Reaction time (h)	Conversion (%)		Selectivity (%)						
	Acetone	1-BuOH	MIBUK	2-heptanone	2-heptanol	2-ethylhexanol	6-undecanone	6-undecanol	Higher MW Products
1.25	79.4	63.1	0.9	46.1	2.6	1.7	36.4	0	6
2.5	92.7	93.0	0.1	13.2	6.4	2.6	57.7	7	8
5	94.1	95.4	0.2	11.9	7.9	2.5	51.6	12.9	7.9
7.5	92.0	97.0	0.2	12.7	10	2.4	43.5	18.1	7.6
10	92.7	98.6	0.1	10.6	7.1	1.7	46.9	20.1	8.3

Table S8. Chain elongation of ABE model mixture in catalytic coupling reaction

Conversion (%)			Selectivity (%)									
acetone	1-BuOH	EtOH	2-pentanone	4-heptanone	2-heptanone	2-heptanol	2-ethylhexanol	4-nonanone	4-nonanol	6-undecanone	6-undecanol	Higher MW. products
87.3	99.9	99.9	4.3	1.5	14	3.4	0.1	16.5	2.5	41.1	5	9.6

2.1 Experimental data related to mechanistic questions of the catalytic coupling of AB or ABE mixtures

2.1.1. Investigation of higher alkylation products in the product mixture

Guerbet reaction consumes 1-butanol to produce 2-ethylhexanol and competes with the main reaction pathway, alkylation of acetone. However, 2-ethylhexanol is valuable since itself it contains 8 carbon atoms as precursor of C8 alkanes. It is possible, that 2-ethylhexanol undergoes further reaction with acetone, in a similar fashion as 1-butanol. To verify this, 2-ethyl hexanol separately was reacted with acetone and the products indeed clearly showed the higher Mw alkylation products.

Figure S4. Catalytic alkylation of acetone with 2-ethylhexanol using Mg-Al-PMO catalyst and Raney Ni. Left: GC-FID chromatogram of the product mixture assigning all major components. Right: bar graph showing substrate conversion and product selectivity. Reaction conditions: 200mg Mg-Al-PMO and 15 mg Raney Ni catalyst, acetone (2.70 mmol, 0.2 mL), 2-ethylhexanol (0.42 mL), heptane (2.1 mL, solvent), dodecane (0.22mmol, 50 μ L, internal standard), 200 $^{\circ}$ C, 20h.

Table S9. Catalytic alkylation of acetone with 2-ethylhexanol using Mg-Al-PMO catalyst and Raney Ni. Analysis of the product mixture.

Conversion (%)		Selectivity (%)								
Acetone	2-ethylhexanol	MIBUK	2-ethylhexanal	5-ethylnonan-2-one	5-ethylnonan-2-ol	7-ethyl-2-methylundecan-4-one	7-ethyl-2-methylundecan-4-ol	5,11-diethylpentadecan-8-one	5,11-diethylpentadecan-8-ol	Higher MW. products
82.6	69.3	2.9	4.4	59.6	11.9	2.2	0.5	13.5	0.5	4.1

2.1.2. Gas phase analysis in order to determine the presence of decarbonylation

Next to the main coupling pathways resulting in the formation of ketones, the corresponding alcohols were also detected. The hydrogen equivalents from these reductions may originate from the Tishchenko pathway (dehydrogenation of the formed hemiacetal upon reaction of butanal and butanol) as well as decarbonylation resulting directly from 1-butanal or other aldehydes. When 1-butanal undergoes decarbonylation, the corresponding propane will also be present in the gas phase. In order to gain insight, we performed analysis of the gas phase by GC-TCD. During the reaction, the pressure increased to 10 bar at 200 °C and decreased to ~1 bar when cooling to room temperature. The gaseous products were collected with a 5mL gastight SampleLock Hamilton® syringe. To do this, additionally 1 bar argon was introduced. This was necessary since the evolved gas amount alone was insufficient for GC-TCD analysis. The gas composition after exclusion of the inert gas is presented in the following diagram and table. From the analysis, the expected carbon monoxide as well as propane can be clearly seen. A significant amount of carbon dioxide as well as hydrogen can be detected, these may originate from water gas shift reaction of a portion of CO with the water formed during the various aldol condensation processes.

Figure S5. Gas phase analysis in order to determine the presence of decarbonylation. Right: Volumetric composition of the gas phase after catalytic alkylation of acetone with 1-BuOH in the presence of Raney® Nickel and PMO catalysts in a 15 mL autoclave. Left: reaction pathway leading to the formation of propane and carbon monoxide. Reaction conditions: 1bar Ar, catalysts (200mg PMO, 15mg Raney® Ni), acetone (2.70 mmol, 0.2 mL), 1-BuOH (5.46 mmol, 0.5 mL), acetone-butanol molar ratio 1:2, Heptane (2.1 mL, solvent), dodecane (0.22mmol, 50 µL, internal standard), 20 h, 200 °C.

Table S10. Volumetric composition of gas phase after catalytic alkylation of acetone with 1-BuOH, reaction conditions as above.

Hydrogen	Volumetric composition (%)			
	Carbon dioxide	Propane	Carbon monoxide	Methane
46.2	27.5	11.3	7.5	7.4

3. Experimental data related to the hydrodeoxygenation of products obtained upon catalytic coupling of AB or ABE mixtures

Table S11. Optimization of reaction conditions using model compound 2-heptanone GC selectivity of the HDO products. Reaction conditions: 15mL autoclave, 2-heptanone (0.5 mL), 10 mL Hexane, 40 bar H₂, 220°C

Reaction time (h)	Temperature (°C)	Selectivity (%)		
		Heptane	2-heptanone	2-heptanol
6	220	87.8	11.1	0.8
12	220	100	0	0

3.1. GC-FID traces of mixture before and after hydrodeoxygenation

Figure S6. GC-FID chromatogram of a product mixture obtained after catalytic alkylation of acetone with 1-BuOH. Reaction conditions: Catalysts (200mg PMO, 15mg Raney® Ni) acetone (2.70 mmol, 0.2 mL), 1-BuOH (0.5 mL), hexane (2.1 mL), dodecane (0.22mmol, 50 μ L), 200°C, 20h.

Figure S7. GC-FID chromatogram of a product mixture obtained upon HDO of the **AB** coupling mixture. Reaction conditions: 15mL autoclave, catalyst: 100mg Ni@Al₂O₃-SiO₂, coupled **AB** product mixture in Hexane (~12 mL), 40 bar H₂, 220°C, 12h.

Figure S8. GC-FID chromatogram of a product mixture obtained upon HDO of the ABE coupling mixture. Reaction conditions: 15mL autoclave, catalyst: 100mg Ni@Al₂O₃-SiO₂, coupled **AB** product mixture in Hexane (~12 mL), 40 bar H₂, 220°C, 12h.

3.2. Results of hydrodeoxygenation of AB and ABE mixtures

Table S12. Product yields obtained upon HDO of AB mixture

Coupling reaction time (h)	Yield (%)	
	Total carbon	Total carbon in C7+
2.5	78.4	60
5	86.0	63.9
10	86.6	66.2
20	88.9	70.5

Table S13. Product yields obtained upon HDO of ABE mixture

Coupling reaction time (h)	Yield (%)	
	Total carbon	Total carbon in C7+
20	84.0	61.3

3.2.1 Sample calculation of carbon yield of AB mixture

Firstly, the starting materials carbon content is calculated. Secondly, the carbon content of the clean alkane mixture determined based on GC-FID measurement and dodecane internal standard. The maximal carbon content is 359.8 mg, the total carbon content of hydrodeoxygenated coupled sample is 319.9. Based on this the carbon yield: $319.9/359.8 \times 100 = 88.9\%$

Table S14. Carbon Content of starting materials

Starting materials		Carbon content			
(mmol)		(mmol)		(mg)	(w/w%)
Acetone	1-BuOH	Acetone	1-BuOH	Total	Total
2.7	5.5	8.1	21.9	30.0	64.1

4. Catalyst characterization

The elemental compositions for some of the catalysts (Ni-PMO, Cu-PMO, CuNi-PMO, CuZn-PMO) have been previously determined and published.^{2,5} In this publication the same HTC catalyst precursors were calcined and used in case of (Ni-HT, Cu-HT, CuNi-HT, CuZn-HT), all other composition were freshly prepared and analyzed by ICP-OES.

4.1 PMO catalysts elemental composition

The elemental compositions were in a good agreement with the theoretically expected ones. In case of CoPMO the expected amount of Co²⁺ was incorporated into the catalyst respect to Al, however the magnesium content was lower than expected.

Table S15. Elemental composition of PMO catalysts.

Catalyst	Al (wt.%)	Mg (wt.%)	Cu (wt.%)	Ni (wt.%)	Co (wt.%)	Zn (wt.%)	Theoretical composition ^a	Experimental composition ^b
Mg-Al-PMO	14.0	34.8	-	-	-	-	Mg _{3.0} Al _{1.0}	Mg _{2.8} Al _{1.0}
Ni-PMO	13.0	24.2	-	16.8	-	-	Ni _{0.6} Mg _{2.4} Al _{1.0}	Ni _{0.6} Mg _{2.1} Al _{1.0}
Cu-PMO	11.3	24.0	15.4	-	-	-	Cu _{0.6} Mg _{2.4} Al _{1.0}	Cu _{0.6} Mg _{2.3} Al _{1.0}
Co-PMO	15.0	20.1	-	-	19.4	-	Co _{0.6} Mg _{2.4} Al _{1.0}	Co _{0.6} Mg _{1.5} Al _{1.0}
CuNi-PMO	11.4	23.2	8.1	7.4	-	-	Cu _{0.3} Ni _{0.3} Mg _{2.4} Al _{1.0}	Cu _{0.3} Ni _{0.3} Mg _{2.3} Al _{1.0}
CuZn-PMO	11.4	21.7	16.6	-	-	6.5	Cu _{0.3} Zn _{0.3} Mg _{2.4} Al _{1.0}	Cu _{0.2} Zn _{0.6} Mg _{2.1} Al _{1.0}

a. Based on quantities of metal ions used during co-precipitation. b. Determined by ICP analysis.

4.2 XRD characterization of the crystalline hydrotalcite catalyst precursors and the corresponding PMOs

XRD characterization of the different catalysts before (Figure S9,) and after calcination (Figure S10) was performed. Hydrotalcite-like precursors (Figure S9) exhibit sharp and symmetrical reflections at 11.71, 23.21, 60.61 and 61.81 (ascribed to the diffraction by the (003), (006), (110) and (113) planes) and broad and asymmetric reflections at 34.71, 38.81 and 46.01 (ascribed to the diffraction by the (102), (105) and (108) planes), according to reported data.⁶ After calcination at 460 °C for 24h, the double-layered structure is converted into that of a mixed-oxide composition (Figure S10), where a residual Mg(Al)O phase is visible while no transition metal oxide phase is shown, indicating an homogeneous dispersion of the active metals.⁷ In case of Co20PMO the peaks are less significant and broader which can be attributed to the more amorphous structure of this catalyst, which could be the consequence of the lower magnesium content.

Figure S9. XRD patterns of the synthesized hydrotalcites and corresponding amorphous PMO catalysts

Figure S10. XRD patterns of the corresponding porous metal oxides after calcination

4.3 TEM and Elemental mapping characterization of the catalysts

The most active catalyst system consisting of Raney® Ni and MgAl-PMO also H₂ activated Ni20PMO was investigated by TEM to get a better insight to the catalysts.

In case of Raney® Ni with MgAl-PMO as it was expected the phase boundaries of the physical mixture was clearly seen even after reaction. Similarly, the relatively big pieces of Raney® Ni particles next to the fine MgAlPMO were also seen.

Figure S11. TEM image of Raney[®] Ni (big black particle in the middle) next to MgAl-PMO particles after reaction (a) and elemental mapping (b) of the same catalyst system on an edge of Raney[®] Ni particle with heterogeneous distribution of the elements. Color code: Mg red, Al green, Ni blue.

Figure S12. Elemental mapping of spent catalyst system: (Raney[®] Ni and MgAl-PMO) on an edge of Raney[®] Ni particle at different areas showing heterogeneous composition.

TEM measurements of the H₂ activated Ni₂₀PMO catalyst showed porous structures that did not display any agglomeration of the Ni dopant. This observation is consistent with a homogeneous dispersion of the transition metals throughout the catalyst structure, a fact also confirmed by elemental mapping. Upon activation at 500°C small dots (1-4nm) could be observed by TEM, however we could not clearly differentiate them from the catalyst support

by EDX. To form larger nanoparticles, the activation was conducted at 600°C instead of 500°C, which indeed resulted in the formation of larger Ni nanoparticles (7-10nm).

The catalyst following the standard coupling was also imaged and only a minor decrease in porosity was detected. The Ni nanoparticles were clearly visible on TEM images and indeed demonstrated that the catalyst is stable under the reaction conditions.

Figure S13. TEM image of Ni₂₀PMO with porous structure (a) and elemental mapping (b) of the same catalyst with homogenous distribution of the dopant. Color code: Mg red, Al green, Ni blue.

Figure S14. TEM image of Ni20PMO (H₂ activated at 500°C) with porous structure and with small nanoparticles(a) and elemental mapping (b) of the same catalyst with indistinguishable

distribution of the dopant by EDX. Color code: Mg red, Al green, Ni blue.

Figure S15. TEM image of Ni20PMO (H₂ activated at 600°C) with porous structure and with Ni nanoparticles(a) and elemental mapping (b) of the same catalyst. Color code: Mg red, Al green, Ni blue.

Figure S16. TEM image of spent Ni20PMO (H₂ activated at 500°C) with slightly decreased porosity (a) and elemental mapping (b) of the same catalyst after reaction. Color code: Mg red, Al green, Ni blue.

Figure S17. TEM image of spent Ni20PMO (H_2 activated at $600^\circ C$) with porous structure and with Ni nanoparticles(a) and elemental mapping (b) of the same catalyst with Ni nanoparticles by EDX. Color code: Mg red, Al green, Ni blue. Yellow dotted circle shows a Ni poor area and orange dotted circle shows a Ni nanoparticle rich area.

Figure S18. TEM image of spent Ni20PMO (H_2 activated at $500^\circ C$) at higher magnification to show the Ni nanoparticles (black dots).

Figure S19. TEM image of spent Ni₂₀PMO (H₂ activated at 600°C) at higher magnification to show the Ni nanoparticles (black dots).

5. References

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